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**THE PERFORMER AS
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Investigating Affordances in Networks of “Things”, “Performers”, and “Composers”: The Multimodal Lab as Site of Knowledge Production

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Abstract

This paper builds on a lecture delivered at the Transplanted Roots Percussion Research Symposium (Porto, 2025) and presents findings from a two-day artistic research lab—the first experiment of my doctoral project. The lab explored collaborative entanglements among “performer”, “composer”, and musicking technology, grounded in theories by Rheinberger, de Assis, Gibson, and Barad. Centred on a DIY cassette-tape apparatus, it employed a multimodal approach combining performance, reflection, documentation, and conversation, supported by video, photography, field notes, and ethnographic protocols. The study investigates how roles, affordances, and material agencies emerge through intra-action, demonstrating how knowledge arises not from outcomes but through the unfolding processes of experimentation.

Introduction to My Experimental System

In February of 2025, I conducted a two-day artistic research laboratory (*OpenLab#1.1*) as part of my ongoing doctoral project—the first in a series of experiments belonging to my derived experimental system, where I ask a new “composer” to choose a working concept to explore together—an aesthetic research—while I look microscopically at the interaction and social dynamic—an epistemic research. As a part of my experimental system, I ask that each composer incorporate cassette tape, in any way and with any tools they choose. (While I use the term composer and performer for analytical purposes in my research, they are merely points of departure. Composer and performer are fundamentally understood as fluid, unstable assignments.)

The collaborators in *OpenLab#1.1* included myself (as percussionist and researcher), composer and live-electronics musician Dustin Zorn, and a nonhuman participant: a DIY cassette-tape-reading apparatus built specifically for the lab. Documentary materials included video, multi-channel audio, photographs, annotated lab books, and an ethnographic observation protocol. Central to the lab’s documentation method were what I refer to as reflection-in-action pauses—timed interruptions (every 5–20 minutes) during which an audio cue prompted each collaborator to momentarily stop, reflect, and record spontaneous impressions. These micro-temporal snapshots formed an additional

experiential layer within the data set, offering insight into the shifting feelings, hesitations, and micro-decisions unfolding throughout the process (for further information on reflection-in/on-action, see Schön (1983).)

Figure 1 illustrates the prototype that Dustin initially conceptualized: a plastic ruler mounted on a wooden base with sliding dowels, tape heads, and looping cassette tape—part ruler, part instrument, part sculpture. This model would be iterated four times to create a four-channel instrument or apparatus. Figure 2 shows our final setup with the apparatus in use.

Figure 1: Graphic illustration of the cassette-looping apparatus prototype, courtesy of Dustin Zorn.

Figure 2: The final setup at the end of *OpenLab#1.1* with Dustin Zorn (left) and Katelyn Rose King (right).

Theoretical Framework: Rheinberger, de Assis and a Multimodal Approach

My doctoral project is methodologically grounded in Hans-Jörg Rheinberger's concept of the *experimental system* (Rheinberger 2006). Rheinberger conceives laboratories as generative constellations of instruments, materials, and ideas that yield unforeseen epistemic events. Within such systems, epistemic things—unstable, not-yet-understood phenomena—coexist with technical objects, the stabilized tools that enable further experimentation. Over the course of repeated experiments, these roles may shift: what initially appears as an epistemic thing can become a technical object, and vice versa. Crucially,

an experiment's success lies not in providing definitive answers but in generating new questions that feed back into the evolving research system.

Paulo de Assis (2018) extends this framework into musical artistic research, offering a compelling way to transpose natural-science methodologies into music compositional practice. He invites us to regard composition, rehearsal, and performance as experimental sites where artistic processes unfold through re-performance, reinterpretation, and re-materialization. Rather than treating musical works as fixed entities, de Assis frames them as assemblages of strata—conceptual, material, performative, and documentary. The experiment in de Assis' work acts as a new mode of creation.

Building on these ideas, my labs function as dynamic experimental systems that shift between different modes of doing: building, experimentation, composition, performance, and presentation. These transitions are not merely procedural but epistemic, generating new forms of knowledge through iterative practice.

Wolfgang Heiniger argues that contemporary music is best understood as a multi-modal practice—one that engages not only with sound material but also with relationships, particularly the relational networks produced by digital devices and interfaces in everyday life (2019). The term multimodality, originating in social semiotics (Kress and Leeuwen 2001), refers to communication that interweaves multiple meaning systems, including language, sound, image, bodily gesture, spatial arrangements, and material cultures. Digital technologies intensify these interconnections by making diverse modes accessible within a single medium.

In my labs, I use the term multimodal in three senses:

- As a multi-sensory approach, where visual, sonic, and haptic elements interact.
- As a mode of creation, encompassing the generation of artistic ideas as well as the articulation of knowledge and research questions.
- As shifting modes of doing, moving between building, experimentation, composition, performance, and presentation.

The following observations stem from *OpenLab#1.1* and will contribute to the overall analysis of my experimental system during the concluding stages of my doctoral project.

Observations from *OpenLab#1.1*

Roles, Patterns of Characteristics, and Temporality

The first key observation concerns the instability of roles. Throughout the lab, I shifted among performer, organizer, co-builder, and researcher. These role transitions produced intra-role conflicts, particularly when logistical tasks disrupted musical flow or when documentation demands interfered with co-creation. Dustin similarly expressed tension around responsibilities, seeking clarity that ultimately proved incompatible with the unfolding nature of the process.

Certain patterns of characteristics, or perhaps markers of contingent relations, appeared in various forms. For example, self-presentation was marked differently by each of us: Dustin always recorded his face while making his reflections, I always recorded the objects. Dustin more-often vocally exclaimed his “failures”, while I tended to vocalise my “successes”.

Time, too, emerged as a structuring force. Our collective sense of urgency fluctuated visibly, tracked on a shared whiteboard as tasks accumulated. Calm beginnings gave way to compressed timelines, driven by building closing hours and the approaching open session. This tacit temporal dramaturgy shaped the affective and productive atmosphere of the lab, but was collectively formed and shaped.

Affordances

Initially, I expected the core focus to be the affordances of the newly built cassette apparatus. Drawing from James J. Gibson’s ecological psychology (1979), affordances describe relational action possibilities between an organism and its environment. Yet because the apparatus was in a continuous state of becoming, its affordances shifted unpredictably.

Instead, the more salient phenomenon was the mutual affordances we granted one another. Dustin assumed I possessed extensive tape-loop expertise, which expanded my own sense of capability. Conversely, my expectation that percussion elements would arise led to intra-role conflicts when they did not. These relational affordances became epistemic things, producing new artistic behaviours and insights.

Material Agency

Material agency played a decisive role throughout the lab. Drawing on Jane Bennett’s concept of vibrant matter (2009) and Andrew Pickering’s mangle-of-practice (1995), the apparatus demonstrated liveliness: loops slipped, electronics malfunctioned, tape tension fluctuated, and drill bits resisted. These disruptions demanded improvisation, reconfiguration, and embodied negotiation.

A particularly illustrative example involved attaching a tape head to the wooden base. The process required a coordinated, choreographic entanglement of human bodies, tools, and materials. In another example, Figure 3 shows how the apparatus pulled our audience in towards a try-out session and discussion on tactile improvements. In these moments, technical objects became epistemic as their resistances and limits generated new questions and pathways.

Intra-action in Collective Composition

As a performer-collaborator, I am trying to rewrite my codes around collective composition by meditating on Karen Barad’s notion of intra-action (2007). Unlike interaction, where pre-existing entities meet and react to one another, intra-action means entities emerge through relation. For Barad, agency is not something possessed; it arises in entangled doing. But for Barad, this means that entities are in fact those relations and

Figure 3: Group discussion and try-outs during the open-doors final hour of *OpenLab#1.1*.

encounters they find themselves in. One is not an independent entity, but the existence of the presence of others.

In our lab, “percussionist”, “composer”, and “apparatus” were not predefined roles but effects of ongoing entanglement. The apparatus itself enacted cuts—moments that defined what could or couldn’t occur. When a tape loop snapped mid-performance, we didn’t repair it: the break became part of the piece. Such moments weren’t failures but transformations that redefined the system’s possibilities.

Through this lens, epistemic things and technical objects continually swapped positions, dissolving the boundaries between tool, collaborator, and outcome. The lab was not *in* a room—it *was* the room: a living network of human and nonhuman agencies.

Perhaps we can design labs not only to test new musical ideas but also to retrieve knowledge about who we become in collaboration. This might prove particularly helpful for performers and performance educators, to develop a practice-based understanding of collaborative intra-action.

The Multimodal Lab as a Generative Experimental System...

This first lab inaugurated my devised experimental system: *epistemic things*—roles, affordances, and material resistances—generated new questions, while *technical objects*—tools, reflection methods, and apparatus—stabilized the process just enough to make those questions visible. Rather than aiming for a finished piece, the lab produced conditions for artistic becoming, where identities and possibilities emerged through practice.

I propose that the multimodal artistic research lab operates through four intertwined principles:

1. **Non-linear structure**—No fixed goal or “piece”. Aims emerged and dissolved; the process itself became compositional.

-
2. **Defamiliarization**—Traditional hierarchies of composer and performer were suspended; each learned the other’s tools.
 3. **Iterative instability**—Malfunctions became material, not mistakes.
 4. **Momentary crystallization**—The final showing was not closure but a snapshot of entanglement, extended by audience discussion as an additional epistemic layer.

Each mode—performance, reflection, documentation, conversation—constituted a distinct aesthetic output, forming a multimodal ecology of creation. Roles, affordances, and material agencies intersected in ways that continually generated new questions. This suggests that multimodal labs may be particularly effective for performers and artists seeking to understand how identities and artistic possibilities emerge through collaborative intra-action.

... and Pathways for Further Inquiry!

Referencing Rheinberger (2006) once more, the experiment and laboratory ultimately reveal more questions than answers. At this point in my project, some analytical as well as philosophical questions have crystallized from *OpenLab#1.1*:

- Are creative outcomes shaped by the affordances we humans have of each other?
- Might we become new practitioners within each collaborative encounter? If so, how do we exist between encounters—or, as Barad might argue, are we always in and of our encounters?
- What happens if we abandon fixed ideas of who we are in projects and instead allow the experimental system to generate who we become?

Conclusion

The findings of this lab support an understanding of human-nonhuman collaboration as a form of generative entanglement. Drawing on Rheinberger, de Assis, and Barad, this paper argues that knowledge in artistic research emerges not only from outcomes but through the dynamic interplay of roles, materials, and temporalities. The multimodal lab is not simply a site for making music; it is a machine for producing alternative modes of creation and reflection.

Each iteration becomes another movement in a larger composition of practice—collective, material, and reflective. By embracing intra-action, we shift from viewing collaboration as the meeting of separate entities to understanding it as a process of mutual becoming. This reframing invites us to design artistic research environments that privilege openness, instability, and transformation—conditions under which new identities, practices, and questions can continually emerge.

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Nemesis: Conciliating Opposites and Questioning Traditional Roles in Musical Creation

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Abstract

This presentation discusses a musical co-creation process conducted by three composers in direct collaboration with an instrumentalist, within a theatrical performance where music holds equal importance to text and dramaturgy. In this interdisciplinary context, the composer assumes the role of musical facilitator, actively embracing the creative decisions of the performer and dissolving the traditional hierarchy between them.

Inspired by practices such as John Cage's indeterminacy, John Zorn's game pieces, and Cornelius Cardew's open scores, the project emphasizes improvisation, collective negotiation, and active listening as essential tools. The traditional figure of the composer becomes diluted, giving way to a collaborative dynamic where composition is shared and shaped based on the performer's initiatives.

The developed methodology particularly highlights the importance of clearly and objectively describing sonic objects and gestures. To achieve this, it draws on theories of listening and sonic description proposed by Pierre Schaeffer and Denis Smalley, as well as Walter Thompson's practice of soundpainting. These approaches underscore the linguistic challenge inherent in communicating musical ideas, making active listening crucial for effective and democratic dialogue between composers and performers.

Finally, the presentation critically addresses the absence, within Portuguese music schools, of pedagogical models that transcend the binary perspective of composition and performance. It argues that collaborative practices represent valuable educational alternatives capable of fostering horizontal, experimental, and creative musical learning.

Introduction

We are a duo that inhabits the gap between two persistent labels—performer and composer—and no longer fit neatly into either. Our collaboration emerged within the crossover project *Nemesis*, where it was necessary to create music that could breathe with the scene and reinvent itself with every rehearsal. The founding gesture was both simple and demanding: to take the tension between opposites as a driving force rather than a problem to be solved. Composition and improvisation, rule and freedom, writing and listening coexist within a shared field of practice where difference remains alive without demanding synthesis.

The question that drives us is direct: how can collaborative musical processes dismantle

traditional hierarchies of composition and performance, proposing instead an ecology of listening and co-decision? We seek a terrain where authorship circulates—where those who propose and those who execute share decision-making—and where the score functions as a light structure: a set of minimal instructions that guides without fixing.

Our work situates itself within a genealogy that runs from John Cage and Cornelius Cardew to the practices of Pauline Oliveros, Brian Eno, and John Zorn—traditions in which composing means designing conditions, and the game of rules replaces the closed score. It also dialogues with the acousmatic thought of Schaeffer (2017) and the spectromorphological listening of Denis Smalley (1997), both of whom treat sound as a phenomenon to be observed rather than an object to be named. Furthermore, it aligns with the paradigm of *research-creation* as formulated by Robin Nelson (2013) and Emma Cocker (2023), where practice is simultaneously a method and a material of reflection.

This article describes the process that sustains a performance—an attempt to condense into six pages a journey of several years of experimentation that we are only now beginning to systematize within the context of our doctoral research.

We propose three main contributions:

1. A replicable protocol—our *game*—that connects sonic references, objective descriptions, and performative action in an iterative cycle;
2. The analysis of a performative case presented in Porto, which shows how the protocol translates into concrete choices—economy of means, polyrhythm built from few sounds, interplay with tape, and negotiation on stage; and
3. The pedagogical implications of a model that shifts music education from reproduction toward an inventive ecology of listening, decision, and co-authorship.

We write from practice to understand practice. *Némesis* asserts itself in this in-between space—where making, listening, and learning become inseparable; where error is material, sound is thought, and the work never concludes, it only keeps happening.

Method: Composing Improvisation

Process Design (macro → micro → macro)

The method unfolds in a continuous macro → micro → macro cycle, where each phase informs the next and reenters the previous.

Macro. The starting point is dramaturgy: we define atmosphere, internal rhythm, tension, and density. This layer guides the desired kind of sonic presence—the sound should converse with the scene instead of just illustrate it.

Sound moodboards. We then create listening panels composed of excerpts, recorded textures, and descriptions of acoustic qualities. They function as shared compasses, training collective perception and identifying transferable properties—duration, intensity, regularity, attack, decay. This is an exercise in *acousmatic listening* (Schaeffer 2017):

hearing sound for what it is, not for what it represents.

Micro. From there we enter the operative level—games of minimal rules, such as “use two sounds”, “organize a 3:2 polyrhythm”, or “transform regularity into irregularity on the third cycle”. These constraints select specific parameters and reduce indecision. The economy of means sharpens gesture and precision in negotiation: with few timbral elements, each variation gains weight.

The core idea is simple: misunderstanding as compositional material. Translating verbal language into sonic action is always imperfect—and that friction is fertile. Execution never fully matches description; deviation generates invention. Rather than correcting, we cultivate error as a creative operator.

The game repeats the cycle *describe* → *perform* → *listen* → *adjust*. Verbalization refines perception; performance returns nuance; and the operative lexicon expands with each round. A practical form of *aural sonology* (Thoresen 2007) emerges, where listening and speaking become one gesture.

Each session ends by returning to the *Macro*: the tested material reenters the dramaturgy and is evaluated by how it breathes with the scene. This consolidates mobile forms—open sequences, coherent yet always reconfigurable.

To compose improvisation, then, is to design conditions, document choices, and cultivate the deviation that transforms error into a tool and listening into a method.

The Game (Central Device)

We call *The Game* the operative core of the process—a method that turns listening into action and communication into composition. An example of the application of this method was the object of our presentation at the Transplanted Roots Symposium 2025. The structure remains stable, but the outcomes never repeat: each cycle is a controlled deviation, an improvisation within shared conditions.

- a. Individual listening. One person listens alone to a reference excerpt—instrumental, electroacoustic, or from everyday life. The goal is not to recognize the source but to perceive the behaviour of the sound: how it moves, transforms, and fades.
- b. Description. The listener then describes what was heard using a vocabulary of qualities inspired by Pierre Schaeffer: short/long, strong/weak, regular/irregular, dirty/clean. Instrumental labels (“xylophone”) are avoided in favour of operative adjectives (“short, regular attacks; dry timbre”). This verbal translation introduces the first productive misunderstanding—the space where listening becomes language.
- c. Execution. The performer interprets the written description in sound. The text becomes gesture, filtered through the performer’s technique and sensibility. Literal fidelity is irrelevant; what matters is the coherence between description and result, the honesty of the gesture in relation to the text.

-
- d. Iterative adjustment. A collective listening follows, accompanied by brief negotiation (“more regular?”, “drier?”). The description is refined, the sound reworked, and the cycle begins again. The shared vocabulary gains precision: the group learns to *speak sound* and *hear language*.

Adopting the precepts of Art-based Action Research proposed by Jokela and Huhmarniemi (2019), this circuit creates continuous feedback—from individual listening to collective sound and back to description—transforming imperfect translation into compositional material. There is no hierarchy: the describer proposes, the performer interprets, and meaning emerges from the oscillation between saying and sounding.

The Game situates itself in the lineage of Cage (1967; 1978), Cardew (1967; 1971), Oliveros (1971; 1989), and Zorn (1987), where the focus shifts from the finished work to the collective behavior that produces it. Sound becomes a consequence of relation, not of individual intention.

It operates simultaneously on three planes:

- as a listening exercise, training attention toward qualities rather than names;
- as a light compositional system, generating material through description;
- as a pedagogical model, where error and hesitation become tools for invention.

Materials and References

The exercise presented in Porto began from three contrasting references: *Psappha* by Iannis Xenakis, *The Anvil Chorus* by David Lang, and *Kaiju Eats Cheeseburgers* by Sylvain Darrifourcq. These works served as points of departure rather than models, allowing us to extract operative principles and translate them into game rules.

From Xenakis, we drew interest in rhythmic architecture: moving blocks of energy, metric variation, and the tension between pulse and impulse—a minimal grammar that fuels the game.

From Lang, we absorbed the idea of obstinate repetition: steady pulse and micro-deviations, a formal austerity that turns precision into fatigue and sound into psychological space.

From Darrifourcq, we borrowed irregular physicality: hybrid timbres (wood, metal, electronics) and the play between predictability and chaos—a model of productive instability.

To these references, we added a pre-recorded tape of continuous noise—an element of disruption and listening. It introduces an alien temporality, one the performer cannot control but must negotiate with, establishing an *acoustic dialogism*: each gesture responds to an invisible presence. More than *style*, what we sought was *behaviour*: from Xenakis, variable density; from Lang, radical economy; from Darrifourcq, fertile imbalance. The material thus becomes research matter—the game converts listening into language and

language into renewed listening, each reference functioning as a pedagogical micro-world for exploring principles of relation and sonic attention.

Questions in Transit: What We Carry, What We Bring Back

Every performance is also a way of thinking. What we bring to the stage is not only sound but a set of questions about how creation, listening, and learning can happen together. What we bring back are new ways of seeing the process itself—questions returned, reformulated, sometimes unanswered. *Némesis* operates as a continuous field of experimentation, where practice and reflection fold into one another.

Investigating by Doing

The game confirms Robin Nelson's principle: the creative process does not precede research—it *is* research. It does not illustrate a theory; it creates the space where theory and practice question each other. Each session is a laboratory of listening and decision-making, where ways of composing, negotiating, and reacting are put to the test.

Repetition with small variations reveals gestures that work and failures that think. In this sense, composing improvisation means thinking through listening—following the movement by which sound transforms into tacit knowledge, a knowing that manifests in the tuning of intentions.

Inspired by Schaeffer (2017), Smalley (1997), Thoresen (2007), Thompson (2006), and Oliveros (1989), we treat descriptive listening as a critical tool: translating sound into words means converting sensation into hypothesis. Terms like “short”, “clean”, or “irregular” cease to be aesthetic adjectives and become operative categories. Language serves to tune listening, and listening serves to tune language.

The Stage as Laboratory

During the performance in Porto, the audience reacted to our choice of references—Xenakis, Lang, and Darrifourcq—questioning their condensation into a short exercise. That response confirmed what the game seeks to expose: the value of creation lies in the process itself, rather than in the finished work.

The live session was more a demonstration than a concert; its value lay in the transparency of micro-decisions, in the audible misunderstandings and reformulations. What is usually called “unfinishedness” here becomes a methodological strategy: it makes visible the interval between intention and realization—the space where learning happens, we think.

The audience's discomfort is part of the device. When the stage declares itself as laboratory, listening shifts—it becomes self-aware. This exposure of process aligns with a lineage from Cage (1967; 1978) and Cardew (1967; 1971) to Oliveros (1971; 1989) and Cocker (2023): to create is to rehearse uncertainty, to turn error and hesitation into instruments of shared attention.

Tools and Derivations

During the post-performance conversation, someone remarked that the game behaved like a form of artisanal artificial intelligence—a system of human prompts generating sonic responses, evaluating them, and reformulating. The analogy holds: both operate iteratively, exploring variation through minimal instructions.

But there is a crucial difference: presence. In the game, friction is physical: bodies translating language into gesture, listening negotiating error, hesitation turning into sensuous data. Technology may expand the field of experimentation, but the core remains human: risk, body, and relation continue to be the fundamental units of invention.

The project's future lies in deepening this collective intelligence. Next steps include documenting the process more carefully—through light scores and annotated videos—and extending the field of experimentation to pedagogical and community contexts, where different levels of sonic literacy can reconfigure the game. The goal is not to perfect a method, but to keep asking.

Synthesis

Between rigour and improvisation, between what is already known and what has not yet been heard, *Némesis* remains in a state of productive tension—a moving field of listening where art and education meet again, not to fix answers but to keep the conversation alive.

Conclusion

In *Némesis*, composing and performing have ceased to be distinct gestures: both inhabit the same circuit of listening and invention, where every decision reconfigures what the work can become. The piece does not fix itself—it happens. It ceases to be an object and becomes a relation, an ecology of presences in continuous transformation.

The research has shown that to improvise is to imagine, listen, and think, and that composing can also teach. The game protocol generated artistic material while simultaneously cultivating listening, decision-making, and co-authorship—rare competencies in both musical practice and formal education. Perhaps this is where a creative process can shed light into other areas of human activity by feeding on the potential of horizontal collaborative practices instead of hierarchical interactions.

The process dissolved boundaries between performer and composer, between rule and chance, between word and sound. What emerged was an ecology of practices where doing and learning blur together, and where error, listening, and deviation become engines of creation.

Némesis persists in that in-between—fragile, vibrant, and always adjusting—reminding us that to understand is not to master, but to listen to what is still coming.

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Toward a Feminist Organology: Moya Henderson, Sekko, and Genealogies of Resistance

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Abstract

This research proposes a feminist organology as a speculative framework for interrogating the epistemic, material, and relational conditions of instrumentality in Western art music. Drawing on feminist genealogy, historiography, and archival research, it traces Australian composer Moya Henderson's 1976 work *Sekko*, and her subsequent invention of the Alemba: a keyboard percussion instrument comprising three chromatic octaves of tuned triangles. Despite Henderson's pioneering and often controversial contributions to Australian contemporary music, her visionary approach to instrument design and its interface with percussion has been largely overlooked. Through engaging with feminist, post-humanist, and decolonial discourses, this research argues that Henderson's practices disrupt normative hierarchies and totalizing orthodoxies within percussion history, while also reflecting on how constructs of power occupy spaces and perpetuate privileges that sustain inequalities in cultural and creative practices. Furthermore, it examines how instruments operate as sites of gendered labour and resistance, exploring the potentials of feminist organology to invite new forms of expression, phenomenological understanding, and object-oriented ontologies.

Introduction

Originality was my first consideration, and experimentation is still a very strong requirement for my work. But now I see originality as a part of the creative process that flows from my overriding requirement of honesty ... Being true to yourself often means experimenting and going against accepted ways of writing music.

—Moya Henderson, quoted in Donald (1986, p. 62)

Australian scholar and composer Andrew Ford posits in *The Shortest History of Music* that “alongside any history of change there will always be continuity” (Ford 2024, p. 2). I take this insight as a frame for examining the tensions between continuity and progress in contemporary musical epistemologies and practices. Western art music is deeply entangled in the complex web of relations that bind power and knowledge. Its histories and practices are shaped by institutional economies, discursive norms, and the inherited canonical conditions that govern what can be imagined, enacted, and embraced in our present creative ecosystems. I argue that the aspects in which we are governed by, constitute the kinds of persons we take ourselves to be, and therefore, politics are a matter of the personal, and inseparable from life itself (Gutting 2005). Thus, there is no

clear line drawn between those on the side of power, and those on the side of resistance (Foucault 2003). Therefore, it is imperative to render visible other ways of thinking, acting, and co-constituting in the present. Acts that are in relation to our “pleasures, labours, troubles, hopes, aspirations”, and subsequently our freedoms (Foucault 2003, p. ix).

Michel Foucault’s notion of genealogy offers one such movement of thought, exploring how our present has taken shape through successive attempts at resolving historical resistances. Therefore, genealogy offers a mode of inquiry that neither seeks origins, nor inscribes linear histories. Instead, it critically traces the circuits linking knowledge and practices, mapping deviations within the apparatuses that govern bodies and actions (Foucault 2003).

Genealogical and archival work often begins in seemingly unpromising places. It demands a meticulous labour to locate and unsettle historical narratives, frequently with sites deemed peripheral: correspondence, notes, diaries, letters, institutional refusals etc. Scholar Sara Ahmed describes the fragile composition of such an archive as part of the work of living a feminist life, where feminism is a fragile archive of “shattering and splattering”: practical, yet messy, critical, and incomplete work, whose fragility imparts a responsibility “to take care” (Ahmed 2017, p. 17). These messy “crisscrossing, overlapping, and interconnected ways that one exists in life” (Thomas-Durrell 2023, p. 170) are crucial sites of knowledge for understanding how our present has taken shape (Mellor 1988). From this perspective, this work engages in tracing feminist genealogies: a speculative method that interrogates musical histories through their doings, reciprocities, and resistances (Lloyd-Jones 2024).

Naming a project speculative or attempting to trace histories signals a critical approach to reading the present. As Maria Puig de la Bellacasa asserts, speculative projects connect “to a feminist tradition” in which thinking about what is “possible” means enquoteprovoking political and ethical imagination in the present (Bellacasa 2017, p. 7). Therefore, this research does not offer a linear reading of history, or chronological biography, but rather it is concerned with a feminist genealogical reading of Australian composer and instrument inventor Moya Henderson’s 1976 work *Sekko: for its water*—a composition for solo percussionist and sculpture, consisting of twenty-seven triangle-like objects.

Rather than framing Henderson’s innovations as pragmatic progressions, this research argues that Henderson’s instrument design and compositions emerge through resistances to the apparatuses of Western art music: the implicit and explicit network of rules that regulate composition, instrument design, and performance practice. Through this line of inquiry, *Sekko* becomes a theatre of procedures: a work that exposes, reconfigures, and disrupts historical norms, through situated knowledges and co-constituted entanglements (Foucault 2003; Barad 2007; Haraway 1988). From this conceptual ground, I tentatively propose a feminist organology—a critical orientation and conceptual framework for thinking through Henderson’s work. *Sekko*, together with her subsequent invention of the keyboard percussion instrument, the Alemba, opens movements of thought that trace the fault lines of the organological conditions in the present. Hen-

derson's instruments can be read as sites of gendered labour that critique institutional economies and foreground embodied techniques of making through acts of feminist inquiry. Thus, Henderson's oeuvre offers a compelling case for this conceptual move. Feminist work does not always offer solutions, but rather solidarities; therefore, this synthesis seeks to interrogate how knowledge is understood, and to open possibilities for thinking and doing otherwise (Lipari 2009).

Contingency and Formation: Henderson's Early Trajectories

Born in 1941, Australian composer Moya Henderson's love for music began in early childhood, yet the first decade of her adult life was spent as a nun of the Sacré Coeur, before severing ties with the church in the 1960s to study composition at the University of Queensland (Macarthur 1988). This biographical trace is offered not as a story of origins, but as one of the many complex contingencies that shaped Henderson's later negotiations with institutions and subsequently, her creative practice. Often described as autodidactic, Henderson arrived at the Hochschule für Musik and Tanz in Köln in 1974, under the primary mentorship of Mauricio Kagel, and peripherally with Karlheinz Stockhausen (Volans 2025). Drawn to the emergent field of Neue Musiktheatre, where irony, parody, and the absurd function as catalysts for creativity and resistance, Henderson quickly achieved notable success, including winning the Kranichstein Prize at the 1974 Darmstadter Ferienkurse für Neue Musik for her composition *Clearing the Air*. In 1976 during Henderson's second year of studies in Cologne, through the trust of her teacher Mauricio Kagel, she embarked on a collaboration that would profoundly shape her creative trajectory: a commission from Düsseldorf based artist Helfried Hagenberg to compose for his sculpture *So-no-re*. This encounter resulted in Henderson's composition *Sekko*, a unique work that was pivotal in initiating Henderson's sustained exploration into instrument design.

Sonic Entanglements: *So-no-re*

Helfried Hagenberg (1940–2022), an artist and professor at the Fachhochschule Düsseldorf, created *So-no-re* in 1974 as a sound sculpture he conceived as part of his broader series of psaligraphic works. Comprising 27 individual triangle-shaped instruments, *So-no-re* was designed to function as a singular, unified sounding instrument. To refine its acoustic properties, Hagenberg collaborated with acoustician Bernd Enders, to extensively analyse the harmonic spectrum of each "triangle" (Figure 1). Each of the 27 objects were suspended individually on fine nylon fishing line, spaced approximately 40 centimetres apart. Visually, the sculpture presents a gradual transition: the front beginning with the shape of a triangle, progressing through nine increasingly square like forms until reaching the shape of a square, then evolving through nine more shapes into a circle, and finally returning through nine further transformations to complete the cycle back at a triangle.

To compose for the sculpture, Henderson developed a unique tablature notation in which the lines and spaces of the staff correspond to an individual triangle, with each triangle receiving a number from 1 to 27. One sonic challenge that Henderson found

was that the lengths of steel of the triangles were all close to the same length, approximately 710mm long with a circular diameter of 10mm each. This resulted in only a range of eight semitones for the entire sculpture. To address this, Henderson collaborated closely with the percussionist Nicholas Bardach of Christoph Caskel's percussion studio, exploring the timbral possibilities of *So-no-re*.

Figure 1: Helfried Hagenberg's *So-no-re* (1974), Münster Gallery exhibit (Image © Helfried Hagenberg, provided by and used with the permission of Monika Hagenberg).

To address the sonic and temporal limitations of *So-no-re*, Henderson undertook a series of experiments using metal, rubber and wooden beaters, fine wire brushes, and even kitchen whisks. She also further explored a repertoire of playing techniques, from dampening with hands and beaters, varying hand and striking pressures, and creating “vibration tones” by applying resonators above and below the objects to amplify their fundamental tones (Henderson 1984, p. 9). Eventually, by attaching plastic “bottle-resonators”, Henderson recalls that she “had managed to stumble onto a unique method of greatly enhancing the otherwise silent sounds of triangles. That was just the start of my journey” (1984, p. 9). This moment underscores how Henderson's innovations emerged through pure curiosity, through embodied experimentation in a domestic setting, rather than through institutional or formal instruction on composition.

***Sekko* and the Theatre of Procedures**

Premiered by Nicholas Bardach at the Hochschule für Musik und Tanz Köln on the 16th of March 1976, Henderson titled her composition, *Sekko: for its water*, a play on words reflecting the conditions of the sounds and their manifestation (Figure 2) (Henderson 2025).

From a critical lens, the premiere can be read as a tension within the institutional apparatus—an event that frames and legitimizes experimental work, offering conditions of visibility and privilege that might otherwise remain inaccessible. Yet, *Sekko* also marks a pivotal historical juncture in Henderson's creative trajectory, underscoring her curiosity of complex acoustic phenomena and instrument design. Each of the 27 objects in *So-no-re* became a site of sonic investigation, generating a catalogue of techniques for

Figure 2: Nicholas Bardach premiering *Sekko* at the Hochschule für Musik and Tanz Köln, Aula, 1976 (Image © Helfried Hagenberg, provided by and used with the permission of Monika Hagenberg).

Sekko and for Henderson moving forward. This process extended beyond conventional compositional or notational practices of the time, exploring objects of banality in the everyday domestic space, highlighting the contingent and embodied nature of Henderson’s approach to composition.

Henderson recalls:

Suspending a triangle on a length of cord just outside my kitchen in Cologne in order to try out an array of kitchen utensils as beaters for the instrument because I was hoping to produce some new and unusual sounds. I had also cut a plastic mineral water bottle in half and, for no apparent reason, held the bottom half against the cord which was supporting the triangle. I struck the triangle and was amazed at what I heard. Unwittingly, and very simply, I’d set up the conditions for the emergence of a quite new sound . . . It was a beautiful sound, and I knew I was onto something.

—Henderson (1984, p. 9)

This anecdote underscores how feminist experiences often manifest outside of conventional compositional frameworks, merging through experimental gestures that demand alternative vocabularies, syntaxes, styles, and forms. Such practices, I argue, can be understood as feminist resistances (Foucault 2003; Mellor 1988). Subsequently, Henderson adopts these “forms of resistance” as her starting point: experimenting with simplistic, unassuming domestic items alongside *So-no-re* to reimagine the ontologies between composer, percussionist, and object (Foucault 2003).

Although limited in its pitch variability, Henderson understood *So-no-re* as Hagenberg intended, as a single dynamic instrument: a theatre of procedures, where the rules of percussion, staging, collaboration, and embodiment were radically reconfigured. Approximately 20 minutes in duration, *Sekko* culminates in a striking visual and sonic gesture: the performer moving in five circular revolutions, in the centre of the triangular frame, arms extended with long wire brushes between the fingers, beginning slowly and accelerating in speed and revolution (Figure 3). This finale is not a mere spectacle,

but the materialization of a conceptual project: a performative gesture of resistance inscribed sonically and spatially on the performers body, the holistic spectral instrument, and the concert space. Bardach later credited this physical approach to performance with teaching him about “stillness as a performer” (Bardach 2025). Such reflection further foregrounds the embodied nature of *Sekko*, where technique is not prescribed or given, but co-constituted through performer-composer negotiations.

Figure 3: Score example from page 21 of Moya Henderson’s *Sekko* (Unpublished score, image © Moya Henderson, used with permission).

Radical Organological Futures

Henderson returned to Australia in late 1976, marking the beginning of a radical engagement with instrument design that unsettled normative paradigms of percussion practice in Australia. Despite the precariousness of freelance life, Henderson declared that, by 1977, she was “irrevocably involved with triangles”, developing what she called resonator-triangles—objects inspired by “Sekko” and Hagenberg’s sculptural aesthetics (Henderson 1984, p. 9). Henderson subsequently designed over three chromatic octaves of resonator-triangles (C3 to F5), an impractical yet visionary set of objects that reimaged the humble triangle as a dynamic sonic assemblage. This work accentuates feminist organology with the potential to imagine new entanglements of corporeality, materiality, and sonic agency.

Henderson’s insistence on the possibility of the triangle persisted throughout the late 1970s and early 1980s, culminating in the invention of the Alemba (Figure 4). Constructed from triangular steel rods with an apex open, each triangle of the Alemba was connected to a quarter-wave tubular resonator via a taut cord and diaphragm, with the instrument encased in a functional wood frame. The instrument was first prototyped and refined during Henderson’s inaugural Australia Council residency in 1983.

By 1985, Henderson had extended the Alemba’s range to include a treble and bass instrument, introducing a tuning system that resonated not only with triangle’s fundamental pitch, but also with its octave and twelfth. Henderson’s radical innovations were trialled with professional contemporary ensembles such as the Percussions de Stras-

Figure 4: Moya Henderson with the Bass and Treble Alemba, 1985 (Image © Moya Henderson, used with permission).

bourg, Synergy Percussion, and the Sydney Symphony Orchestra (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Score example from page 19 of Henderson’s composition *Alanbiq* (1977/1985), originally composed for the Percussions de Strasbourg, later amended for Synergy Percussion (Unpublished score, image © Moya Henderson, used with permission).

Into the 1990s, Henderson further developed the “Tosca Bell”—a pentangle design offering expanded geometric parameters for tuning multiple vibrational modes of the triangle (fundamental, octave, twelfth, minor third). To develop the Tosca Bell, Henderson collaborated with physicists and engineers, conducting empirical tests using finite element modelling (Figure 6). These experiments examined the acoustic potential of the pentangle and soundboard, components meticulously designed to enhance resonance across the instruments range, functioning similarly to a piano or harpsichord soundboard (Fletcher 1984). Such processes foreground Henderson’s curiosity and determination to discover new forms of musicking, rendering visible what Foucault might describe as the conditions of existence (Gutting 2005, p. 48) for feminist approaches to instrument design (2003). Therefore, Henderson’s work challenges normative organologies and opens dialogue for alternative material agencies for keyboard percussion.

Toward a Feminist Organology

Tentatively, through Henderson’s work, I propose the conceptual framework of feminist organology. This is not a taxonomy or a fixed system of classification, but rather a criti-

Figure 6: Chart for measuring frequency spectrum/experiments with Pentangles (Image © Moya Henderson, used with permission).

cal orientation: a “new organology” that interrogates the epistemic, material, relational, and social conditions of instrumentality (Tresch and Dolan 2013). A feminist organology therefore asks: what is being classified, why, how, and under what conditions? It examines instruments as sites of gendered labour and acknowledges the embodied negotiations that shape our relations and doings in practice (Magnusson 2017, p. 291; Tresch and Dolan 2013). Unlike traditional organology—which privileges lineage, progression, and origins—a feminist organology, although speculative, underscores the provisional, reciprocal and contextually embedded nature of musical knowledge, resisting totalizing orthodoxies and the assumption that instruments are neutral objects to be exploited, asking critically: what epistemologies shape and prescribe our musical present?

Subsequently, I argue that Henderson’s work is feminist inquiry, as it exemplifies this conceptual orientation. Her improvisations with the banal, alongside complex sculptural aesthetics, reveal inventions that emerge through embodied encounters rather than transactional, hierarchical, or institutional modes and prescriptions. Therefore, *Sekko* reconfigures the lore and hierarchies underpinning percussion histories, disrupting relations between composer, performer, and instrument, and challenging assumptions embedded in post-instrumental discourse (Stene 2014). Thus, a feminist organology takes such reconfigurations and resistances as starting points for its inquiry: as tools to interrogate the conditions under which musical conventions, and the canons they sustain, are produced and replicated in the present.

Although *Sekko* is posited as the protagonist in this research, Henderson’s later inventions must be read as sustained continuations of feminist resistance: instruments of sonic, tactile, and agential speculation that resist classification. These instruments are not easily defined or categorized, are rarely acknowledged, and do not sit within the canonical repertoires, techniques, or discussions of the art of percussion. Henderson’s trace thus supports feminist organology as a speculative and provocative frame through which to think anew. It imagines instruments as fragmented yet dynamic assemblages, entangled with bodies and histories, and asks of percussionists: who are “we” in the present?

Therefore, I do not claim feminist organology as an established discipline, rather, I offer this research as provocation—a way of imagining what might be possible when reading instruments and histories through feminist genealogies of resistance. What does such a framework enable one to think? With whom can we think alongside? What new conceptual work could emerge through the lens of a feminist organology?

Conclusion: Provocations for Thinking Otherwise

This research, while speculative, traces the feminist genealogies of Moya Henderson's experiments in percussion and instrument design. In doing so, it offers feminist organology as a way of reimagining percussion instruments as dynamic assemblages, entangled with bodies, and histories, and invites new ways of conceptualising and enacting musical relations. Subsequently, this research asks: what might percussion look like if feminist organology were embraced as a critical orientation? What is the highest dream we could dream (Torrence 2025)?

This work honours Donna Haraway's call to make trouble—"to settle and rebuild" (Haraway 2016, p. 1)—to foster historical manifestations of kinships and to explore feminist narratives as practices of care and collective thinking, as articulated in the statement that "it matters what stories we tell to tell other stories with; it matters what knots knot knots, what thoughts think thoughts, what descriptions describe descriptions, what ties tie ties" (Lloyd-Jones 2024, p. 35). Therefore, by tracing Moya Henderson's work and acknowledging *Sekko/So-no-re* as a catalyst for her subsequent instrument designs, this research reveals the potential of feminist organology as a conceptual framework for sustained feminist critique of the structures of power and knowledge in Western art music.

Henderson's instruments have much more life to be lived, and although they resist definition and categorisation, they can be understood through Henderson's radical lived experiences, artistic tenets, and the genealogies they generate. Thus, to think through Henderson's work via feminist organology is to invite dissent, multiplicities, and critical celebration. It invites a critical historiographic reading of percussion's formation and successions, one that disrupts fixed absolutes of the past, and reframes them as contingent possibilities for sense making in the present.

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Excerpts for Percussion from the Brazilian Orchestral Repertoire

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Abstract

This article analyzes percussion excerpts in the Brazilian orchestral repertoire, highlighting their technical, musical, and stylistic relevance. Works by Brazilian composers like César Guerra-Peixe and Claudio Santoro offer challenges comparable to international excerpts, incorporating regional rhythms, specific articulations, and virtuosic demands. Focusing on the xylophone, snare drum, cymbals, and tambourine, the study emphasizes the uniqueness of Brazilian writing and advocates for its systematic inclusion in orchestral training, promoting greater appreciation of Brazilian symphonic music globally.

Introduction

Brazilian orchestral repertoire, although rich, is little explored in the academic and pedagogical training of symphonic percussion, which still relies mainly on European and North American traditions. Brazilian production, however, offers works with refined writing, high technical demands, and strong cultural identity, ranging from 19th- and early 20th-century composers such as Carlos Gomes and Alberto Nepomuceno to the post-1922 Modern Art Week period. Still, the presence of this repertoire in concerts is limited, and its academic approach lacks systematic study (Gianesella 2012).

This article aims to situate Brazilian percussion writing within the orchestral context, showing how specific excerpts can serve as pedagogical tools for technical and stylistic training. We will focus on four excerpts frequently listed by Brazilian orchestras—xylophone, snare drum, cymbals, and tambourine—and suggest other national works that fulfill similar functions.

Xylophone

The xylophone, part of the keyboard percussion family alongside the marimba, vibraphone, and glockenspiel, is one of the most requested instruments in orchestral auditions due to its presence in numerous works and the possibility of performing fast, virtuosic passages. Each instrument in this family has distinct characteristics, such as vibration mode, key materials, use of resonators, types of mallets, and range (Moore 1970).

The technical demands of the xylophone include rapid diatonic and chromatic passages, divergent hand movements, rhythmic complexity, rolls, mallet doubling, and the use of more than two mallets (Alford 1983). Many excerpts combine several of these challenges.

A frequent example is the opening of George Gershwin's *Porgy and Bess* (1935) (Figure 1), included in Brazilian, North American, and European audition lists. This excerpt requires time control, precise mallet technique, evenness of notes, sound quality, and attention to modulations, being fast and virtuosic both as a solo and within the orchestra (Alford 1983). The combination of technique, rhythm, and syncopated accents explains its constant presence in auditions.

Considering these characteristics, it is possible to suggest Brazilian excerpts that present similar technical challenges.

Figure 1: Xylophone excerpt from the introduction of *Porgy and Bess*. Transcription by author.

César Guerra-Peixe—*A Retirada da Laguna* (1971-1972)

Composed between 1971 and 1972, *A Retirada da Laguna* is one of César Guerra-Peixe's most emblematic works, though it is rarely programmed by Brazilian orchestras. It gained visibility through the "Brasil em Concerto" project (Itamaraty/Naxos), notably with the first participation of the Goiás Philharmonic in 2016, including the work on their debut CD (*Brasil em Concerto* 2016). The second movement, "Alegria em Nioaque", contains challenging xylophone passages between measures 85 and 100, featuring fast runs and unison sections with the orchestra, similar to those in *Porgy and Bess*, making it suitable as an excerpt for percussion auditions.

Figure 2: Xylophone excerpt from “Alegria em Nioaque”, mm. 85–100. Transcription by author.

The excerpt from “Alegria em Nioaque” resembles *Porgy and Bess* in tempo (120–130 bpm), use of sixteenth notes, and phrase modulations. Another movement, “Regresso Pacífico” (measures 59–71), presents similar challenges, with demanding mallet technique and a tempo of 120 bpm, though with a slightly more restrained character (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Xylophone excerpt from “Regresso Pacífico”, mm. 59–71. Transcription by author.

Snare Drum

The snare drum, or military drum, is one of the oldest percussion instruments, historically associated with marching and infantry (Marcuse 1964). It can vary in size, body materials (wood or metal), and snare (gut, metal, etc.). It is usually the first instrument studied by percussionists, serving as a foundation for technique and rhythmic reading. Its practice involves traditional Swiss techniques, including single and double strokes, ornaments (flams), and rolls, frequently required in audition excerpts (Alford 1983).

Snare drum excerpt from *Peter and the Wolf*

Another frequently requested audition excerpt is from *Peter and the Wolf* by Sergei Prokofiev. The snare drum is valued for evaluating a percussionist’s virtuosity and control, often used in the first phase of auditions as a “confrontation piece” to screen candidates.

In this excerpt, sixteenth-note triplets in 4/4, alternating with eighth notes and rhythmic precision, stand out, requiring an interpretation with a military character, described as “vigorous and brave” (Goldenberg and Cirone 2002, p. 12).

49 L'istesso tempo
Solo S.D. (Tamb.mil.)

50

51

Figure 4: Snare drum excerpt from *Peter and the Wolf*, op. 67, by Sergei Prokofiev, rehearsal nos. 49–51. Public-domain score.

César Guerra-Peixe—*A Retirada da Laguna* (“Regresso Pacífico”)

Still within César Guerra-Peixe’s *A Retirada da Laguna*, the ninth movement features, right at its beginning, a particularly interesting snare drum part with elements requiring technical skills similar to those in the Peter and the Wolf excerpt, including challenges found in other commonly requested excerpts, as will be discussed later. It is worth noting that, in terms of character, this movement is also military, as indicated by the marking “*Alla Marcia*”.

Figure 5: Snare drum excerpt from the beginning of the ninth movement of *A Retirada da Laguna*. Transcription by author.

The first beat with four thirty-second notes requires precise technique. Although in 6/8 and marked piano, this excerpt from *A Retirada da Laguna* is suitable for auditions. The rhythmic cell repeats 13 times until rehearsal 1, where a sixteenth-note triplet appears, similar to the Prokofiev excerpt.

Figure 6: Snare drum excerpt from the beginning of the ninth movement of *A Retirada da Laguna*. Transcription by author.

Complementary Instruments

“Auxiliary” or “accessory” instruments include cymbals, tambourine, triangle, castanets, bass drum, and others. Although the term may suggest lesser importance, they appear in much of the orchestral repertoire—often more than the snare drum or key-

board instruments—and require specific techniques. They are mandatory in auditions, with cymbals and tambourine among the most requested.

Due to the variety of these instruments, it is impossible to master them all completely. Thus, although works after the 20th century explore Latin percussion (bongos, congas) and Eastern percussion (temple blocks, gongs), auditions generally focus on standard instruments: cymbals, bass drum, tambourine, triangle, and sometimes castanets.

Tchaikovsky—*Romeo and Juliet* (Cymbals)

Like *Porgy and Bess*, the cymbal part in *Romeo and Juliet* is frequently requested in auditions. It requires precise technique, careful timing, and short, homogeneous strokes, achieved by damping the cymbals against the body to maintain rhythm (Alford 1983).

Figure 7: Cymbal excerpt from *Romeo and Juliet* (Overture-Fantasia), TH 42, by Pyotr Ilyich Tchaikovsky, rehearsal letter E. Public-domain score.

Claudio Santoro—Symphony No. 7 (Cymbals)

As in Tchaikovsky, the technique required to perform this passage is essentially the same. The eighth notes are also played short, using the same damping technique mentioned by Alford (1983). Similarly, the passage ends with long, open notes. We can infer that the same technique studied for *Romeo and Juliet* can be applied to this excerpt from Symphony No. 7.

Figure 8: Cymbal and bass drum excerpt from Symphony No. 7, movement II, "Brasilia", mm. 62–67. Used with permission of the rights holder (Alessandro Santoro).

Georges Bizet—"Aragonaise" from *Carmen Suite No. 1* and Emmanuel Chabrier—*España* (tambourine)

The excerpts from *España* (Chabrier) and *Carmen Suite No. 1* (Bizet) are well-known both in auditions and in music history, highlighting the influence of Spanish sonorities, especially in France, with instruments such as castanets and tambourine. These passages require a good sense of style and agogic interpretation to convey the colors and character of Spanish music. Technically, they are challenging: in the "Aragonaise" from the *Carmen Suite No. 1*, the tambourine maintains a constant pulse, demanding precision to avoid destabilizing the orchestra.

Figure 9: Tambourine excerpt from the beginning of second movement ("Aragonaise") from *Carmen Suite No. 1* by Georges Bizet, orchestrated by Ernest Guiraud. Public-domain score.

In *España* by Emmanuel Chabrier, particularly in the excerpt shown in Figure 10, the difficulty arises from the fast tempo, requiring the percussionist to employ technical alternatives, such as playing the passage on the knees. As in the "Aragonaise", the tempo must be very steady and secure, in addition to executing extremely clear articulation.

Figure 10: Tambourine excerpt from *España* by Emmanuel Chabrier, mm. 61–77. Public-domain score.

César Guerra-Peixe—*Suíte Pernambucana*

The *Suíte Pernambucana* reflects influences from Northeastern Brazilian music, with writing close to the original sound of popular rhythms, as researched by Guerra-Peixe. In the “Frevo” movement, the tambourine maintains a fast rhythm, using techniques similar to those in *España* and “Aragonaise”, including playing on the knees and soft dynamics in the opening measures.

Figure 11: Beginning of the last movement (“Frevo”) of the *Suíte Pernambucana*.

In a single excerpt from a truly Brazilian piece, containing traditional and folkloric elements, the composer presents writing that challenges the percussionist, requiring technical solutions that not only ensure accurate and precise performance but also highlight the musical character of the “Frevo”.

Conclusion

Nowadays, more works by Brazilian composers are being revisited and recorded, increasing access to compositions that were previously forgotten or poorly documented, although the number is still insufficient compared to the country’s concert music output. Interest in joining orchestras has also grown, and today there are more professional, youth, social, and church ensembles. Despite this, the repertoire remains bound to tradition, repeating the same excerpts and leaving out contemporary works that require modern techniques. The musician’s specialization process, centred on auditions, ultimately limits the percussionist, a situation also observed in orchestras outside Brazil. This research does not propose replacing classical excerpts but rather including passages that enrich auditions, especially Brazilian works that have long been under-explored. The aim is to expand the audition repertoire, ensuring that percussionists are prepared to perform folkloric passages or tambourine parts in the daily orchestral context, avoiding incorrect interpretations.

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Idiomatism and Performance Aspects in the Use of the Berimbau in Two Solo Works

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Abstract

This article examines the berimbau, a percussion instrument deeply rooted in Brazilian popular and traditional culture, within the context of concert music. The recital featured two solo works by Brazilian composers—*Matiz III*, “*Ciclos*” by Rodrigo Lima and *Íris* by Alexandre Lunsqui—which explore the technical, timbral, and expressive potential of the berimbau. These compositions expand the instrument’s techniques and idiom, highlighting its role beyond traditional contexts and fostering a dialogue between popular music and concert music. The study also analyzes the characteristics of the works, their references, and the challenges posed to performers. By engaging with non-conventional instrumentations, this research contributes to the training of percussionists interested in exploring Brazilian instruments within the contemporary repertoire. The use of the berimbau in these pieces encourages an encounter between musical traditions, inviting performers to engage with the expressive and symbolic layers of an instrument deeply connected to Afro-Brazilian heritage. The project investigates how this dialogue enriches both the performer and the repertoire, opening new interpretative and technical pathways.

On the Research, the Berimbau, and Idiomatism

The use of percussion instruments associated with Brazilian popular and traditional music within the context of concert music has been steadily increasing. This article analyzes the berimbau from different perspectives of performance in two Brazilian solo percussion works: *Matiz III*, “*Ciclos*” by Rodrigo Lima and *Íris* by Alexandre Lunsqui. The particularities of the instrument, its modes of execution, and interpretative solutions for the new idiomatic proposals formulated by each composer are discussed.

From these contrasting approaches, this research addresses possible paths toward a fully developed interpretation, considering how composers bring timbres from Brazilian popular music into a new language and, consequently, into a new context. This process fosters encounters between different musical genres and encourages investigations into performers’ training profiles, the techniques required, and the challenges inherent in this repertoire. The study thus reflects on the trajectory of the concert music performer when engaging with an instrument laden with elements and ancestral ties to popular culture, analyzing the relationship between these contexts and their role in expanding both the instrumental idiom and the performer’s technical–performative repertoire.

When consulting the description of the berimbau in Mário D. Frungillo's *Dicionário de Percussão* (2003), it becomes evident that the author initially presents capoeira as the musical genre in which the instrument is most frequently employed, as illustrated in the following excerpt:

Berimbau, a struck chordophone. . . identified with the dance-game of capoeira, has been sporadically used in Western art music. In capoeira, at least one instrument is used, and in Angola-style capoeira three are employed, known as gunga (low), médio (middle), and viola (high), generally with sizes corresponding to pitch height . . .

—Frungillo (2003, p. 39, translation by the author)

Due to the lack of historical documentation, it is not possible to determine precisely when the berimbau became associated with capoeira; however, by the early twentieth century it was already part of this practice and had become its symbol. Kay Shaffer, in *O Berimbau-de-barriga e seus toques*, describes the berimbau as a musical bow, stating that “in general, it is constructed from a flexible piece of wood held in an arched shape by a steel wire, with a gourd attached to the lower part. It is played together with a caxixi—a type of rattle” (Shaffer 1977, p. 20). Traditional mastery of the berimbau proved fundamental to the interpretation of the works analyzed. Prior knowledge of the instrument’s assembly and tuning, technique, timbre, and characteristic gesturality provided a concrete reference from which it was possible to understand the alternative explorations proposed in the compositions. This traditional experience consolidated a bodily and sonic memory that guided the adaptation to new materials—such as different mallets, suspension methods, the use of objects, and extended sound exploration—allowing these demands to be interpreted with control, coherence, and idiomatic sensitivity, even outside the berimbau’s original cultural context.

Figure 1: The berimbau and its accessories. Photograph by the author.

Figure 1 indicates each element that constitutes the berimbau. The wooden bow is known as the verga, and the baqueta (stick) may be made from the same wood as the verga. The figure also shows the dobrão, a large coin which, in traditional performance practice, is held between the thumb and index finger, in the same hand that supports

the instrument with the middle, ring, and little fingers. The coin is used to tension the string, causing it to sound a pitch one tone higher than the open string, which may also be achieved using a small, smooth stone.

The works by Lima and Lunsqui are also analyzed from the perspective of berimbau idiom. According to Pavan (2009, p. 39), as cited in Miranda (2018, p. 15), “in the etymological origin of the word idiomatic, *idio* derives from the Greek *ídios*, meaning that which is proper, personal, or distinctive.” In musical research, the term may refer to the characteristics inherent to a particular instrument or style. Thus, instrumental idiom encompasses:

the peculiarities and technical and expressive possibilities that a given sound medium affords. . . Among the aspects covered by the term are: specific performance techniques; physical and mechanical possibilities; expressive potential; typical compositional procedures; the level of feasibility of such procedures; and knowledge of relevant works for the medium, among others

—Kreutz (2012, p. 3), as cited in Miranda (2018, p. 16, translation by the author).

By articulating traditional practice, idiomatic characterization, and the insertion of the berimbau into concert music, this study delineates the parameters that guide the present investigation. These elements serve as a foundation for interpreting the technical and expressive demands proposed by Lima and Lunsqui, as well as for understanding the construction of a specific instrumental idiom that emerges from the dialogue between tradition and contemporary musical language. The following sections analyzes *Matiz III*, “*Ciclos*” and *Íris*, highlighting the compositional and performative procedures that reconfigure the berimbau in each work, in addition to proposing practical solutions that enabled their performance according to the composers’ demands.

The Berimbau in *Matiz III*, “*Ciclos*” and *Íris*

Composed in 2013, *Matiz III*, “*Ciclos*” presents the berimbau as the leading instrument, responsible for the exposition of the thematic material and for providing the compositional material that structures the entire work. Written for multiple percussion, the piece employs a suspended berimbau in combination with a pair of bongos, a low-pitched drum, a metal reco-reco, a Thai gong, and two Chinese gongs. The rhythmic cycles, inspired by Indian talas, are introduced in the opening measures through the berimbau and recur at various moments in the other instruments.

In the performance notes of the score, the composer specifies that the berimbau must be suspended for the execution of the work, leaving it to the performer to determine the form and mechanism used for this suspension. In our setup, we used a bongo stand to support the instrument; however, we identified the need to avoid direct contact between the wood of the berimbau and the metal of the stand, as such contact would dampen its resonance and alter its characteristic timbre. For this reason, we suggest covering the metal surface with rubber or foam only in the area that comes into contact with the wooden bow of the suspended instrument. Figure 2 documents the final setup adopted for the performance of the work:

Figure 2: Setup for *Matiz III*, “*Ciclos*”. Source: Authors’ archive.

Figure 2 also shows the positioning of the berimbau’s gourd (*cabaça*) oriented laterally in relation to the instrument, directing the sound toward the audience and ensuring that its volume is not lost amid the drums and gongs, which have greater sound projection. In the first measure of the work, Lima indicates that the berimbau may be played with the wooden shaft of the mallets. However, during our investigations, we observed that a standard multiple-percussion mallet has excessive weight for the instrument’s string, increasing the risk of breakage—a situation that occurred several times during the early stages of practice. As a solution, we opted to use a stick specifically designed for playing the berimbau. Its lighter weight, combined with striking the string as close as possible to the *cabaça*, preserves the instrument’s characteristic timbre without compromising the integrity of the string, while also facilitating the production of the fundamental pitch corresponding to the berimbau’s tuning.

We observed that the compositional demands of the work require the simultaneous use of four mallets, enabling the performance of instruments with different classifications and timbral qualities, as well as the execution of complex passages. The Leigh Howard Stevens technique (Stevens 1979), which avoids crossing the mallets, proved to be the most suitable for playing the berimbau, as it allows greater freedom and fluidity of movement, in addition to a more efficient rebound. For the drums, gongs, and wood block, the Gary Burton technique (Burton 1965)—characterized by crossed mallets—proved more effective, providing greater stability for rapid passages between the drums. Thus, two distinct techniques are employed simultaneously in sections 1 and 3, where the berimbau is present, while in the intermediate section, without the berimbau, the metal *reco-reco* is also played using the Burton technique in order to achieve greater agility and control.

The solutions proposed for the performance of *Matiz III*, “*Ciclos*” highlight the exploration of the berimbau through a structural logic based on rhythmic cycles and its integration into a multiple-percussion setup, underscoring both the technical complexity of this transposition and the expressive versatility of the instrument. From these con-

siderations, the discussion moves to the analysis of *Íris*, a work in which the compositional treatment of the berimbau unfolds according to different aesthetic and gestural premises.

Composed in 2012, *Íris* employs the berimbau exclusively, exploring a wide range of techniques and interpretative resources. A wooden stick, a grooved metal stick (“parafuso”) for scraping, stones, a metal tube, a bamboo reco-reco, a caxixi, and a cord used to suspend the instrument on the performer’s body are employed according to the composer’s demands. The work expands the berimbau’s timbral possibilities by incorporating sound explorations, harmonic sounds, and unconventional methods of sound sustain, while simultaneously integrating traditional techniques and sound practices associated with the instrument.

Preparing the berimbau became essential for the feasibility of the work. During our studies, we identified the need to glue a small piece of sandpaper between the cabaça and the wooden bow in order to prevent the gourd from slipping and consequently causing detuning due to the intense movements characteristic of the performance. A more resistant wire also proved to be more suitable for withstanding the strikes and scraping gestures with the metal stick. In Brazil, most capoeira masters and berimbau makers use wire extracted from car tyres; however, we obtained wire extracted from truck tyres, which proved to be more resistant and better suited to the purposes of both works discussed here.

Figure 3: Setup for *Íris*. Source: Authors’ archive.

In *Íris*, Lunsqui does not explicitly suggest that the berimbau be suspended; nevertheless, from the very beginning of the piece, the notation for the right-hand stick played simultaneously with the left hand striking the cabaça with the fingers indicates the need to suspend the instrument in a way that does not compromise its natural resonance. The setup illustrated in Figure 3 shows the different sticks and objects used in the work, as well as the cord employed to suspend the instrument around the performer’s neck, allowing the use of both hands throughout the performance:

Figure 3 also shows two stones placed on the table to the performer’s left, which allow

the execution of the three pitches prescribed by the composer for the berimbau string—a technique that does not exist in the instrument’s traditional performance practice. In this way, it becomes possible to produce different pitches without the need to support the berimbau by holding it with the left hand, while simultaneously maintaining the two stones between the thumb/index and index/middle fingers, ensuring the instrument’s characteristic resonance. We also emphasize the importance of using porous stones or stones with some degree of surface grip, in order to prevent slipping due to perspiration during performance. This ensures the precise tension point required for each pitch on the string, while also allowing the necessary balance to hold the instrument simultaneously.

Some resources derived from the traditional manner of playing the berimbau are also incorporated into the work’s requirements, such as striking the string with the tip of the wooden stick to extract the lowest sound, characterized by the presence of the instrument’s fundamental pitch. To achieve this, it is likewise necessary to play as close as possible to the point of contact with the cabaça. The use of the caxixi, a complementary instrument traditionally associated with the berimbau, is also present in the work, appearing at a climactic moment that leads to the conclusion. In this same passage, the composer indicates the use of the dobrão, a metal coin traditionally employed in berimbau performance; however, this object does not produce the desired sonic glissando required by the piece. For this reason, we chose to replace the dobrão with a small metal tube, which allows for the production of a more audible and resonant sound. At the end of the work, the composer indicates the need for a grooved wooden stick to execute a roll on the cabaça. In our experiments, we found that using a thin bamboo reco-reco played along the rim of the cabaça not only produces the desired effect but also yields a more present and projected sound.

The interpretive practice of *Íris* demonstrates that the work requires from the performer a deep understanding of both traditional berimbau techniques and the new sonic possibilities proposed by Lunsqui. The specific preparation of the instrument, the use of non-conventional materials, and the need for suspension reveal a constant dialogue between tradition and experimentation. In this context, prior familiarity with the instrument proved essential to technical feasibility and to the construction of an interpretation consistent with the work’s hybrid language, establishing *Íris* as a significant example of the berimbau’s potential within the contemporary percussion repertoire.

Final Considerations

The works analyzed highlight the growing incorporation of the berimbau and other instruments rooted in Brazilian popular culture into the context of concert music, revealing new technical possibilities and fostering encounters between distinct cultural spheres. In *Matiz III*, “*Ciclos*” and *Íris*, traditional knowledge and practice of the berimbau proved fundamental to the development of viable interpretive solutions, supporting the transition toward expanded techniques and new sonic discourses. The process of adapting the instrument—through suspension, the selection of specific beaters, and the use of various objects—underscores detailed preparation as an essential component of

performance. In this sense, the works expand the performer's technical–performative repertoire and reaffirm the need for an interpretive approach that integrates tradition, innovation, and the aesthetic demands of contemporary music.

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